

2,4-Dihydroxybenzaldehydeoxime-Urea-Formaldehyde Polymer as a Polymeric Ligand

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Attempts to prepare coordination polymers having good thermal stability and catalytic activity have enhanced the development of polymeric materials. Polychelates of oxalic acid catalysed salicylaldehyde-formaldehyde and 2,4-dihydroxybenzaldehydeoxime-formaldehyde polymers with various metal ions have been reported^{1,2}. The present paper describes synthesis and characterisation of polychelates of the 2,4-dihydroxybenzaldehydeoxime(DBO)-urea(U)-formaldehyde(F) polymer (DBOUF) with Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II}, Zn^{II}, oxovanadium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI)

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of polymeric ligand and its polychelates are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1 – ANALYTICAL DATA OF POLYMERIC LIGAND AND ITS POLYCHELATES

Compd.	Analysis% : Found/(Calcd.)				Mol. wt. of repeat unit g/mol
	N	C	H	M	
2,4-DBOUF	17.46 (17.57)	50.71 50.50	4.78 4.60)	—	237.00
[Cu(L ₂) ₂] _n .2nx	14.70 (14.69)	42.03 41.99	4.40 4.19	11.75 11.12)	571.54
[Ni(L ₂) ₂ X ₂] _n	14.75 (14.82)	42.42 42.35	4.27 4.23	9.97 10.35)	566.69
[Co(L ₂) ₂] _n .2nx	14.96 (14.80)	42.30 42.33	4.23 4.23	11.20 10.39)	566.94
[Zn(L ₂) ₂ X ₂] _n	14.90 (14.72)	42.05 42.03	4.20 4.18	11.76 11.39)	573.38
[Mn(L ₂) ₂ X ₂] _n	14.70 (14.92)	41.80 42.63	4.35 4.26	9.88 9.76)	562.93
[VO(L ₂) ₂ X] _{nx}	14.30 (14.61)	41.75 41.74	4.47 4.17	9.04 8.86)	574.94
[UO ₂ (L ₂) ₂] _n	11.45 (11.38)	32.70 32.52	3.35 3.25	30.00 31.71)	738.03

The average molecular weight of DBOUF polymer was found to be 1285 g/mol by VPO. Ir spectra of the polymer show bands at 3 100–3 600 (OH, NH). A sharp but weak band at 2 720 (intramolecular H-bonding)⁴ and 1 640 cm⁻¹ (C=N). On the basis of the results structure I is proposed for the ligand.

I

All the polychelates are amorphous in nature and insoluble in common organic solvents. The elemental analyses (Table 1) agree with a 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry.

A comparison of the ir spectra of the ligand and its polychelates shows that the broad ligand band at 3 100–3 600 cm⁻¹ (OH, NH) remains unchanged, while the band at 2 720 cm⁻¹ disappears from the spectra of the polychelates. This indicates the replacement of hydrogen of the phenolic OH group by metal ions. The lowering of $\nu_{C=N}$ band by 10–20 cm⁻¹ in the polychelates suggests coordination of metal ions through nitrogen of oximino group. The increase in N–O stretching frequency by 30–50 cm⁻¹ confirms the coordination through nitrogen of the oximino group⁵. The oxovanadium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI) polychelates show sharp bands at 970 (V=O) and 935 cm⁻¹ (U=O)⁶. The bands around 550 cm⁻¹ corresponds to the ν_{M-N} vibration⁷.

The magnetic moment of the Cu^{II} polychelate is 1.74 B.M. The reflectance spectrum shows two bands at 15 625 and 25 975 cm⁻¹ assigned to the transition

${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ in a square-planar geometry⁸ and charge transfer transition respectively. The magnetic moment of the Ni^{II} polychelate is 3.29 B.M. which is close to the range observed for octahedral stereochemistry⁹. The reflectance spectrum of the Ni^{II} polychelate exhibits three bands at 9 389, 15 873 and 24 390 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively, considering an octahedral geometry¹⁰. The Co^{II} polychelate has a magnetic moment of 3 70 B.M. which is consistent with the spin-only value for three unpaired electrons in tetrahedral environment¹¹. Its reflectance spectrum shows three bands at 8 772, 16 130 and 23 809 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to ${}^4A_2 \rightarrow {}^4T_1(F)$, ${}^4A_2 \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$ and charge transfer transitions respectively¹². The Mn^{II} polychelate having magnetic moment of 5.23 B.M. is lower than spin-only value (5.95 B.M.) which may be due to partial aerial oxidation of Mn^{II} to Mn^{III} during synthesis, suggesting octahedral structure¹³. The electronic spectrum of the Mn^{II} polychelate exhibits three bands at 13 513, 15 748 and 25 641 cm^{-1} assigned to the ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}({}^4G)$, ${}^4A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}({}^4G)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$, ${}^4A_{1g}({}^4G)$ transitions respectively, considering octahedral geometry¹⁴. The magnetic moment of the oxovanadium(IV) polychelate is 1.79 B.M. which is normally observed for octahedral symmetry¹⁵. The reflectance spectrum of the oxovanadium(IV) polychelate exhibits three bands at 13 333, 15 385 and 26 316 cm^{-1} corresponding to ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$, ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B$ and ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$ transitions respectively, for an octahedral geometry¹⁶. The Zn^{II} and dioxouranium(VI) polychelates are found to be diamagnetic as expected

From the above discussion structure II has been proposed for the polychelates.

II

Thermal and electrical properties : The results on thermal study show following decreasing order of stability : DBOUF > dioxouranium(VI) > Zn^{II} > Ni^{II} > oxovanadium(IV) > Co^{II} > Mn^{II} > Cu^{II} . The polychelates are less stable than the parent polymeric ligand as expected¹⁷. The lowest stability of the Cu^{II} polychelate may be attributed to the catalytic oxidative effect of Cu^{II} . The removal of water above 150° in the polychelates indicates the presence of coordinated water molecules¹⁸.

The negative logarithm of conductivity for the polymer is found to be a linear function of reciprocal of temperature in the range of study. The activation energy (E_a) and specific conductivity (σ_0) of the polychelates were evaluated using the relation, $\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp(-E_a/kT)$, where σ is the conductivity at TK and k is the Boltzman constant. The electrical conductivity at room temperature decreases in the order : DBOUF > oxovanadium(IV) > Ni^{II} > Zn^{II} > dioxouranium(VI) > Mn^{II} > Co^{II} > Cu^{II} , while the activation energy declines as DBOUF > Ni^{II} > Cu^{II} > oxovanadium(IV), Mn^{II} > Zn^{II} > dioxouranium(VI) > Co^{II} ¹⁹.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade DMF and methanol were used after distillation. 2,4-Dihydroxybenzaldehydeoxime was prepared by condensing 2,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde² with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in 70% ethanol.

Polymeric ligand : A mixture of DBO (15.3 g, 0.1 mol), 37% formaldehyde (16.2 ml, 0.2 mol) and 2 M HCl (50 ml) was refluxed with stirring at 60°; urea solution (6.0 g, 0.1 mol in 5 ml water) was added dropwise and the resulting reaction mixture was refluxed at 110° for 5 h on an oil-bath. The solid yellow product obtained was washed with water followed by acetone to remove unreacted monomers. It was purified by dissolving in 8% aqueous NaOH and reprecipitated by adding 1:1 (V/V) HCl/H₂O with constant stirring. Finally, the polymer was washed with boiling water and dried.

Polychelates : To DBOUF (2.4 g, 0.01 mol) dissolved in DMF (50 ml), the respective metal nitrate (0.005 mol) in DMF (50 ml) was added slowly with stirring. The polychelate separated out on addition of

saturated solution of sodium acetate. It was digested for 30 min on a water-bath, filtered, the solid washed with DMF and hot distilled water and dried at 60° for 24 h. In case of the oxovanadium(IV) polychelate vanadyl sulphate was used as the starting material.

Elemental analyses, reflectance and ir spectra, magnetic measurements and thermogravimetric analyses were carried out as described earlier². Average molecular weight of polymeric ligand was determined by vapour pressure osmometry using DMF as a solvent and benzil as a calibrant at 71°. The electrical conductivity was measured with pellets prepared from finely powdered samples at high pressure and using a Hewlett-Packard 4329-A instrument.

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